

1 **HIV infection in B-cell subsets from HIV-1+ humans.**

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6 B cell dysfunction was evident in humans with HIV-1 infection at the transcriptome level. B cells completely
7 lacked expression of *RAG1*. Mixed inflammasome activation was present with activation of *Gbp1* but
8 silencing of *Caspase 10*. B-cells from human with HIV-1 infection activated *Cxcr3* but silenced *Irf4*. Failure
9 to produce a diverse immunoglobulin repertoire in humans with AIDS and advanced HIV-1 infection may
10 be a primary consequence of *RAG1* silencing resulting from HIV-1 infection in the B-cell.

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